

ANALYSIS OF THE ACTIVITIES OF PRIVATE HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article higher education quality in increasing private higher education institutions duties set get , their education in the system place and importance analysis do , private higher education institutions by done being increased affairs and events and their the result analysis do , private higher education institutions higher education institutions between of competition to the body coming and of competition increase in providing duties set get and showing pass , private higher education institutions international education standards answer to give in providing duties identify get , higher education quality in increasing private higher education in institutions done being increased measures analysis from doing consists of

Key words: private higher education , education reforms , innovative education , Uzbekistan , market economy , education quality , high education institution , private higher education institution , state higher education institution , non-governmental higher education institution , higher education system , qualified personnel , professors and teachers .

Introduction . Last in years in Uzbekistan education fundamental reforms in the field done increased , the state and non-state education institutions activities to develop separately attention is being directed . Including private higher education institutions appear to be and their number increase of the country education in the field important from changes is one Private higher education institutions the world scale education quality increase and competition strengthen tool as confession will be done . They are state to the budget the load reduce with together , in education diversification process accelerates . Uzbekistan conditions while this institutions not only state higher education to the system assistant , perhaps innovative education development main from the factors one as is being considered

Private of investment come in arrival is high the largest in our education of our achievements one in 2016 started market relations regarding reforms for higher education comfortable field it has been . The reason simple : from per year grow up went on demand regardless , the state in universities installed acceptance quota in society millions the " market" of uneducated people appear did Numbers : in 2023 state to universities document submitted applicants number of 986 thousand increased although , to them separated acceptance quota is 381 thousand organize did High education coverage increase for private to universities not only daytime , maybe external education organize to do permission to be given this the market business for very attractive by doing sent Alternative offer didn't happen to young people knowledge giving in society positive change to do such as good work to the basis business to build and this through income to find each one businessman dream if no wonder That's it because of and to the proposal proportionate respectively private universities the number last 6 years out of 85 increased went

Main part. In Uzbekistan private higher education institutions organize to be done for main legal base In the 1992 Constitution defined education get the right and last years education reforms . President Shaukat Mirziyoyev since 2017 done increasing education reforms private to the sector wide opportunities created Including :

Admission in 2019 done decisions and decrees private higher education institutions to open and activities in order to put legal in terms of provided .

High in 2021 education institutions autonomy about laws through private sector for innovative development possibilities expanded .

Private higher education institutions country economy and education to the system one how much positive effect shows :

To education investments attraction do : State resources savings and private sector development .

Personnel Preparation : Market requirements suitable personnel fast preparation opportunity Innovative education programs current do : International to standards suitable study programs present to achieve

Market economy Flexibility : Education services in the market competition strengthen

Private higher education institutions in development the following difficulties there is :

Legal and normative restrictions : State control and licensing of processes complexity .

Funding Issues : Private in the sector education services investment attraction in doing difficulties .

Education quality control do : State and private higher education between quality coordination problems

Teacher personnel Lack of : Private education institutions enough level qualified experts attraction in doing difficulties .

Private higher education institutions activity the world in experience wide spread For example :

USA and Great Britain : Non-state universities global education system leader part is considered

South Korea and Japan : Innovative in development private education important role plays

India and Turkey : Private sector through of education fast development and of competitiveness increase provided .

Uzbekistan private higher education system international the experience account taking , education quality increase and competitive environment to create it is necessary

Private education institutions legal benefits to give

Public-private partnership mechanisms development .

International grant and investments attraction to do

Teachers qualification increase programs expand .

Conclusion . Private higher education institutions in Uzbekistan education system important part of the country economic and social development service to do can Education quality increase , innovation current reach and state budget load reduce such as advantages him modern education system indispensable to the part turns That's it with together , there is problems solution to do and international from experience efficient use this of the system stable development provides . Modern in the circumstances state higher education system for - modern to the degree exit and of globalization current problems eliminate reach according to difficult task set gave Society development present stage common medium education

schools , academic high school and profession colleges to graduates worthy higher information to give current being left State higher education socio-economic of activity different in the fields as well management service in the fields of scientific research , economic , technical and another in the fields next to work is located employees to teach intended . High education system future specialists for present to be done skills and special knowledge for in charge and young people modern science and technologies achievements creative to use account received without selected of the profession in vectors theoretical or practical aspects open to give directs . Modern in the circumstances of the country stable development , security , competitiveness goods work release , young people of society different from the segments to universities equal to acceptance in doing of personnel role and importance more and more current being is going

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